

KEYWORDS

**GIS Analysis,
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GIS as a Student Recruitment Tool for Building Hospitality and Tourism Programs

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Abstract

Student enrollments in the Hospitality & Tourism Management (HTM) major have declined at most universities. The purpose of this paper is to identify the demographics of current students and in order to market to similar potential students. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) analyses were employed to identify existing student characteristics. The GIS systems help identify demographics and psychographics of potential students. GIS also aids in learning the location (target markets) of prospective students with similar attributes. A customized *heat map* illustrates where clusters of existing students live, and a GIS technique called *Anselin Local Morans I* was employed to show statistically significant clusters of Census Block Groups. Psychographics was utilized to identify neighborhoods of each student's home. Results indicated that, surprisingly, over 59% of recent HTM students came from affluent households. Very little has been published about how to recruit HTM students. This study seeks to begin this discussion around attracting HTM students into a university.

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INTRODUCTION

The past several years have produced lower-than-expected enrollment figures for many colleges and universities (Newton, 2019) which have included a reduction in Hospitality and Tourism Management (HTM) majors. This downward trend was exacerbated by the recent pandemic, which resulted in a 10% decrease in enrollments from 2020 over the previous year (Sutton, 2021). These disruptive actions have prompted more aggressive recruitment efforts to maintain current levels of HTM majors, without which, many HTM programs may not survive. Currently, there are approximately 200 undergraduate 4-year Hospitality & Tourism programs in the United States, which produce approximately 5,000 HTM graduates each year (Barrows & Bosselman, 1999); therefore, successful HTM programs must actively recruit students to survive. Universities can no longer assume students will keep flooding into their schools, operating under the assumption that if they “build it and they will come” (Pretlow III, 2014, p. 479). Recruitment strategies of all kinds, both old and new, should be implemented in order to preserve current HTM programs. This paper illustrates techniques using Geographic Information Systems (GIS), which assist in target marketing to potential HTM majors for a college program.

While there are many articles that address companies recruiting HTM graduates and universities recruiting minorities and retaining their faculty (Smith & Green, 2021; Choi, Ruetzler, & Wang, 2019; Lin, Chiang, & Wu, 2018), an exhaustive literature search did not uncover a substantial number of papers that addressed HTM college processes for recruiting students into a four-year HTM academic program in the United States of America (Lee, Olds, & Lee, 2010). In fact, there are few papers that address recruiting college students into an HTM program such as Pretlow III (2014), who suggests specific measures to attract HTM students such as personal contact and “multiple exposures” to the recruitment materials. There are studies about majors other than Hospitality and Tourism recruiting college students for their academic major such as Carothers, Aydin, & Houdyshell (2019), who discuss methods they use in recruiting students to become teachers through collaborating with nearby school districts and enticing high school students to pursue teaching as a career. Álvarez (2017) uses summer camp programs involving robotics as a recruiting tool to encourage high school students to pursue a degree at the

robot sponsor's university. Further, Cernauskas, Kelsey, & Houlihan (2018) discuss using more traditional means such as open houses and visiting the college campus during normal class times as a means to increase college enrollments. Alternatively, Reding (2018) presents methods to recruit college majors from local community college students.

While there is limited research about how to attract students to a given university, the topic definitely has not been explored using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) techniques to perform recruiting tasks. Dodds and Muchnick (2008) mention the top three reasons students chose the HTM major was, "the [program's] reputation, teaching, and career prospects" (p. 19). Chen and Hsiao (2009) find their students seeking a good school reputation as well as a convenient location, among other factors (p. 41). Lee, et al., explored Career Development Theory to identify the impact family, friends, and community have on university selection for an HTM program. Surprisingly, they determined that the impact from teachers, family and friends had a greater impact on students' decisions than did the influence of social media. A decade later, Lee, Lee, and Dopson (2019) further verified how important to school choice was the influence of 'traditional factors' such as "faculty, advisors, and parents" (p. 75) and how these persons were more influential than social media. However, there are not studies that share recruiting methods for college level HTM programs. While these studies give insight, they leave a void in recruiting methods used to attract future students. This study helps to fill this gap of how to find and recruit prospective HTM students.

Hossler (1999) discussed recruiting practices and mentioned with regard to attracting college students, "Recruiters in the future will place more emphasis on electronic media, student information systems, statistical technologies, and increased use of geodemographic tools" (p. 15). This study utilized target marketing segmentation analysis that identifies and categorizes current students [customers] in order to market to similar potential students [customers], a method mentioned by Vieveen (2018) as well as Kara and Mkwizu (2020). The research question addressed which characteristics were common among current HTM students in an effort to recruit prospective students whose home location (e.g., where a student's parents live) either shared a similar geographic proximity or similar demographic and psychographic characteristics. Specifically, the research question for this study is:

What are the shared characteristics and attributes of university students and how can these characteristics and attributes be used to recruit others just like them? A pilot study was undertaken using Geographic Information System (GIS) analyses to explore this research question using methods suggested by Hossler (1999) including techniques to identify patterns in the students' address locations as well as demographics and psychographics. Many of these methods were included in the current study, including cluster analysis, demographics, psychographics, and spatial statistics utilizing home addresses of HTM students in the fall of 2017 from a state school in Connecticut, USA. These same methods were used to study the most recent seven (7) years of HTM student enrollment data for this university.

LITERATURE REVIEW

History of Hospitality & Tourism Management Programs

Historically, hospitality and tourism education grew out of apprenticeships and informal training as business owners shared their methods and techniques through on-the-job training. This method was adopted in the U.S. based on European practices, where apprenticeships build a pathway to a career (Barrows & Bosselman, 1999). In the past 50 years, formal education has emerged to better prepare students to fulfill needs of hospitality and tourism employers – even though there is controversy as to the effectiveness of graduates' preparation (Barrows & Bosselman, 1999; Airey & Tribe, 2006). The growth in HTM education now mirrors the growth in the industry (Barrows & Bosselman, 1999) and this growth has allowed programs to develop very specific types of training such as specific Food and Beverage, Gaming, and Club Management specializations.

There are educational programs that prepare graduates for specialization in fields as mentioned in Barrows and Bosselman (1999) where "a student can graduate with a specialization in Baking and Pastry Arts at the Culinary Institute of America; Housekeeping Management at Cuyahoga Community College; Gaming Management at the University of Nevada-Las Vegas; and Club Management at the University of New Orleans" (p. 4). Sigala and Baum (2003) mention trends in education including online education as well as an emphasis on lifetime learning so that graduates will continue to learn more about their industry and keep current on the latest trends as well as an emphasis on low-cost tuition.

Student Recruitment

Although Duffin (2020) forecasts a constant quantity of overall college enrollments for both public and private colleges, the past few years have shown a decline in college-level enrollments, especially for for-profit four-year colleges and community colleges (Newton, 2019). This suggests the need to actively recruit HTM students to prevent declining enrollments. Rudd, Budziszewski, and Litzinger (2014) stress the importance of recruitment as well as retention and “the support of successful alumni, viable internship opportunities, and a knowledgeable faculty and staff” (p. 120). One ongoing strategy, which has also been embraced at this university, is the practice of teaching an introduction to HTM course to attract majors from within the current university student body (Crawford, Hubbard, Gaillard, & Waln, 2009).

While these additional efforts have a direct impact on recruitment, this current study focused solely on the recruitment aspect for enrollment growth. Much of the research on recruitment and retention is either not current such as Digh and James (1994) – who discuss the importance of response times to prospective students – or research relates to areas outside of the United States (Kim, Guo, Wang, & Agrusa, 2007; Kusumawati, 2019; Chen & Hsiao, 2009). While not targeting HTM majors specifically, Hossler (1999) describes some college recruitment issues—specifically how important timing is to the college recruitment process. If materials are sent to prospective students too early, they may be disregarded but if they are sent too late, then the student may no longer be open to considering the given university. This current study is based on student location and income level of students’ parents as illustrated by the figures below.

Location

Conventional wisdom would expect to see Lower income students attend a campus located near to their parent’s home (H1). Alternatively, students from a wealthier family would most likely choose a college irrespective of the distance from their home of origin (H2). While many students may want to attend a

college far away from home, the financial status of their family of origin presumably has an impact on this as indicated in Table 1. Specifically, students from a high-income family are not constrained by the financial implications of attending a school that is far away – they could choose a university that is located close or far away from their family home. Dodds and Muchnick (2008) found that 72% of HTM students they polled identified the university’s location to be an important factor in their college decision. Tobler (1970) defines the ‘First Law of Geography’ as “everything is usually related to all else but those which are near to each other are more related when compared to those that are further away” (p. 236). This suggests that there may be potential students located near existing HTM students. Further, there may also be potential students located near the campus. Therefore, if current clusters of existing HTM students are identified, their neighborhoods (e.g., zip code sub-groupings such as nearby ZIP-Plus4 addresses) can receive marketing materials as demonstrated by Tang and McDonald (2002) in order to market to other students with similar proximity to the university. To determine student family locations, GIS software could be (and was) employed to calculate each student’s home’s distance from campus as mentioned in Hossler (1999).

GIS is a tool that has been used for a plethora of analyses including target marketing, restaurant clustering, and store site selection (Reilly, 1931; Prayag, Landré, & Ryan, 2012; Muller & Inman, 1994). Further, Tang and McDonald (2002) utilized GIS to identify where university students lived to predict where to recruit students with similar backgrounds and/or comparable demographics. Their study involved quantifying and mapping the total number of students within a given postcode (like USA’s five-digit ZIP Code). Additionally, Tang, et al., used these data to forecast from which ZIP codes future students would attend.

Reilly (1931) introduced the concept of retail gravity. Similar to how a planet’s gravity pulls objects toward it, a retail store has a certain level of pull to attract customers based on a customer’s distance from the

Table 1: Distance from Campus

Near	Far
H1: Students from lower income households are more likely to attend a college that is located closer to their home.	H2: Students from higher income households are more likely to attend a college of their choice irrespective of the distance from home.

Table 2: Student's Family Income Level

Lower-income	Higher-income
H3: Students from lower income households are more likely to attend a college that has a lower tuition cost structure.	H4: Students from higher income households are more likely to attend a college of their choice irrespective the college's tuition cost structure.

store and the size and popularity of the store. This can also apply to the gravitational pull universities have for attracting students as suggested by Tang and McDonald (2002). Presumably, students seeking an economically less expensive degree will choose a school that is located closer to their home of origin to minimize travel costs and perhaps living expenses (e.g., students live at home with their parents).

GIS Heat maps are one way to visually illustrate a concentration of Teruel-Gutierrez and Maté-Sánchez-Val (2021) utilize heat maps to display concentrations of Airbnb listings and prices in Barcelona Spain; however, the same methodology can be used in other industries including the purpose of this current paper to identify existing students. Many studies, including Mahdi and Esztergár-Kiss (2021), utilize simplified distance analyses to categorize geographic data points into manageable areas. Additionally, Zhai, Xu, Yang, Zhou, Zhang, & Qiu (2015) used heat maps to demonstrate the popularity of restaurants according to social media posts. Similarly, Magige, Jepkosgei, and Onywere (2020) utilized heat maps to show proximity of hotels to the near Mara Game Reserve, which demonstrates the importance of place and distance on certain analyses indicating that distance plays a large role in the choice of where a student attends college. Based on this, the following hypotheses are offered:

H1: *Students from lower income households are more likely to attend a college that is located closer to their home.*

H2: *Students from higher income households are more likely to attend a college of their choice irrespective of the distance from home.*

Tuition Costs

The study university is a state university with approximately 12,000 students as of 2020 and is arguably one of the two least expensive four-year degree options in the state of Connecticut for studying HTM ("Connecticut Costs," 2019). Connecticut students have other HTM academic options, but many of these private colleges cost significantly more to attend than in-state Connecticut State school tuition. In fact, the University of New

Haven and Sacred Heart Universities are both more than six times as expensive as the study school used for this paper ("Connecticut Colleges," 2019). Mitchell College is another private college that offers an HTM major – at more than five and one-half times the price tag of the study school. While there are many private colleges that offer a hospitality major in Connecticut, there are only two public university options (reasonably priced for Connecticut residents) which offer a four-year HTM degree within Connecticut.

Tuition costs are listed in "Connecticut Colleges" (2019) and identify Connecticut's state universities

Table 3: Connecticut Colleges, Cost and Affordability for 2019

School	Tuition
United States Coast Guard Academy	\$0
All CT Community Colleges [12 campuses]	\$3,816
All CT State Universities [4 campuses]	\$5,424
Holy Apostles College and Seminary	\$7,680
University of Phoenix Fairfield County Campus	\$9,480
University of Connecticut [4 campuses]	\$11,998
St Vincent's College	\$14,520
Post University	\$15,310
Paier College of Art Inc	\$16,600
Lincoln College of New England [3 campuses]	\$18,780
Goodwin College	\$19,998
Lyme Academy College of Fine Arts	\$28,824
University of Bridgeport	\$30,150
Mitchell College	\$30,448
Albertus Magnus College	\$30,650
University of Hartford	\$36,088
Saint Joseph College	\$36,273
University of New Haven	\$36,770
Sacred Heart University	\$39,570
Quinnipiac University	\$44,420
Fairfield University	\$46,490
Yale University Best Value	\$51,400
Wesleyan University	\$52,174
Trinity College	\$52,280
Connecticut College	\$52,530

as the least expensive four-year university options in Connecticut. The study school is one of the four state universities listed on Table 3 on the row entitled, “All CT State Universities [4 campuses].” Although families from all economic situations may choose the study university, lower income families are more likely to choose the study school (or one of the other three Connecticut State Universities) because of its comparatively low tuition. Sigala and Baum (2003) found low cost to be an attractive feature for many prospective HTM majors. Based on these tuition figures, presumably the four Connecticut State schools would be the most viable option for students who come from lower income families or those who seek a reasonably priced tuition.

Alternatively, students who come from a more affluent family would have more college choices because they would be able to afford more expensive schools. Based on this conventional logic, Hypothesis 4 is offered:

Therefore, Hypothesis 3 is presented as follows:

H3: *Students from lower income households are more likely to attend a college that has a lower tuition cost structure.*

H4: *Students from higher income households are more likely to attend a college of their choice irrespective the college’s tuition cost structure.*

Demographics and Psychographics

González-benito and González-benito (2005) discuss how demographics and psychographics can be used as a tool to characterize a given geographic area such as a Census Block Group (CBG). A CBG is an artificially created area designated by the Census Bureau. CBGs typically contain about 1,000 people and are much smaller than a Census tract or zip code; therefore, CBGs are more precise in identifying resident attributes than Census tracts (Krieger, 1992). Although the idea of lifestyle segmentation was introduced in the 1950s, Bell (1958) is noted as making this original correlation between lifestyle and purchasing behaviors. Lazer (1963) and Moore (1963) further extended Bell’s research to include the effect lifestyle had on Marketing efforts – specifically on what purchases were made by similar consumers. Plummer (1974) mentioned how in 1963 William Lazer incorporated lifestyle segmentation into marketing in order to measure “people’s activities in terms of (1) how they spend their time; (2) their interests, what they place importance on in their immediate surroundings; (3) their opinions in terms of their view of themselves and the world around them; and (4) some basic characteristics such

as their stage in life cycle, income, education, and where they live” (p. 33).

These characteristics can then be used to analyze how a given CBG compares to a larger area within a town, city, or state. The GIS software company Environmental Systems Research Institute (ESRI) developed twelve *LifeMode* categories (psychographic groupings) and assigned each CBG an applicable category based on many lifestyle-type factors. ESRI further developed segmentation of each *LifeMode* to create 65 distinct segmented attributes for each block group based on similarities of neighbors including demographics (ESRI, 2014). For decades, psychographics, like ESRI’s Tapestry data, have been used to target specific market segments for various purposes such as advertising, identifying potential customers, and pet adoption to name a few (Krishnan, 2011; Miller, 2008; & Patronek, 2010). Miller (2008) utilized psychographics in analyzing characteristics of visitors to the Pocono Mountains in Pennsylvania and found it to be an effective method to segment customers and target guests ‘like them’ for marketing efforts. He follows a traditional marketing process of profiling current customers and searching for more like them. Barber, Taylor, and Strick (2010) emphasize the importance of using not only demographics, but also using lifestyle segments which add a ‘richer’ view of groups of people. Kucukemiroglu (1999) also supports using lifestyle attributes to better characterize respondents to better understand and categorize them based on similar qualities. Beyond asking merely demographic questions, Kucukemiroglu posed lifestyle-type questions in order to add to the demographic profile of respondents. Raw demographics often don’t tell the whole story and are bolstered with the use of psychographics. Krishnan (2011) adds further evidence to the correlation between purchase behavior and psychographic segments. The findings of Krishnan’s study support previous research that correlates grouping of populations based on similar attributes and buying habits in order to predict specific purchasing behaviors. Further, Parsa, Kreeger, Van der Rest, Xie, & Lamb (2021) utilized psychographics to better explain restaurant failures in a US metropolitan city.

One characteristic of the ESRI Tapestry data that identifies overall CBG affluence within a given CBG is the *LifeMode* categories which indicate affluence within the *LifeMode* name by adding to the *LifeMode* name an ‘I’ for higher-income families and a ‘II’ – e.g., Metro Cities I versus Metro Cities II. In the Metro Cities example above, those CBDs labeled

with the 'I' have higher incomes than those CBDs with 'II' attached to the name. "The 'I' or 'II' appearing after each group name designates the relative affluence within the group, with I being more affluent than II." (ESRI, 2014, p. 12). Therefore, the II segments comprise the low-income students and I segments comprise the high-income students. Based on these segment types, Hypothesis 5 is presented as follows:

H5: *Students' choice of a college is affected by their demographic and psychographic attributes.*

METHODOLOGY

This first paragraph of the methodology section outlines the methods used to analyze and evaluate existing students in order to find others who live in close proximity to them. The rest of the methodology section looks at these techniques in further detail. These methods include geo-referencing (address matching) a student's home of origin in order to apply distance analysis to identify possible recruits from the same geographic locale as existing (or previous) students from this university. Once all students were plotted on the digital map, a heat map was generated to identify the 'hot spots,' which identify locations where a high concentration of students' home of origin exists. A statistically significant tool, Anselin Local Morans I, was employed to augment the visual heat map and utilize Census Block Groups (areas similar in size to zip codes) to statistically identify clustering of students' homes of origin. This paragraph serves as a 'big picture' summary of the remainder of this section.

This current study included students who belonged to either Generation Y or Z. Enrollment for HTM majors at the study school has declined during the timeframe represented in this study. The locations of student's homes were one part of this analysis; therefore, USPS addresses of students' homes of origin were identified to determine if there was a correlation between students' homes' and their proximity to campus. Spatial clustering was used to determine if there were groupings of student homes and specifically if there were groups of students' homes that could be used for marketing campaigns based on location of houses compared to the campus. Each current HTM student's address was collected and all personal information was deleted to protect students' privacy. Each address was then geo-referenced (e.g., 'address matched') to enable viewing each address as a dot on a map. Each of these dots were intersected with CBG areas to link the demographic and psychographic data associated

with each student's home of origin. A heat map was created to visualize the nearness of current students with their proximity to other existing students where darker shades of purple indicate a higher concentration of current students than lighter shades. Although the heat map visually illustrated clustering of students' homes, Moran's I was also computed in order to statistically quantify student clusters within Census Block Groups (CBGs) and verify statistically the visual implications of the heat map. Moran's I statistically confirm clustering as seen visually through the heat map.

A pilot study was conducted using fall 2017 student data from the study school's Registrar's Office for 67 HTM students' home addresses, which were address matched and spatially assigned psychographic classifications by Census Block Group (a U. S. Census Bureau boundary). Also, distances were assessed between students' homes and the study school campus. Additionally, students' home locations were analyzed to assess their proximity to each other in a cluster analysis. This pilot study explored various GIS techniques and analysis tools to determine the best combination of analysis methods to use for the final study. Based on this pilot study, a larger number of student addresses (representing seven years' worth of student data) were utilized for the full study. Including HTM students from the fall of 2013 through spring of 2020. Because students appeared in registration files during multiple semesters, duplicate records were deleted, which left 277 students whose homes were located within the state of Connecticut for this seven-year study period.

Geo-referencing – address matching

Current HTM student's permanent home addresses (e.g., a student's parent's address) for 277 unique student addresses for the seven-year period beginning the fall of 2013 were geo-referenced/ 'address matched' using street address, city, state, and ZIP code to assign a latitude/longitude coordinate on the face of the earth (e.g., a dot on a map). Four students' addresses located outside of Connecticut were not utilized in this study. The process of georeferencing created points for all students' permanent home addresses at the physical address location. 100% of the addresses were matched at an address level, which exceeded the requirements for this study. An address-level match is the most accurate geocoding result. An example of a lesser accurate level would be to locate the

address at the centroid (center) of a 5-digit ZIP code, which is not very accurate.

Distance Analysis

In order to test H1, multiple ring buffers were created to show the distance bands from campus and to capture distances from campus that are less than 10 miles, between 10 and 20 miles, between 20 and 30 miles, between 30 and 40 miles, and greater than 40 miles away. These distances were chosen as a means of segmenting distances away from the study school within the state of Connecticut. Students homes were then summed within the five distance buffers. See Figure 1.

Heat Map

A Heat Map was created to show the concentration of existing students' permanent homes with the long-term goal of trying to recruit other students who live near existing students. Heat maps were borrowed from weather maps to quickly illustrate temperatures across a landscape – specifically, they show hot values typically in red whereas cooler temperatures are typically represented in green shades. The heat map was created using ESRI's Point Density tool located in Spatial Analyst Tools from the GIS software, ArcGIS Pro version 2.5.0. The map symbology was then changed to indicate a white/transparent color where students are not in close proximity to each other. At the other end of the spectrum, purple coloring was designated to indicate a higher concentration of existing students' homes – locations where students' homes are close to one another or are geographically clustered. This analysis only showed where homes were located in proximity to each other and does not consider the location of the campus – how close each student's home is from campus. It merely shows students' proximity to each other.

Anselin Local Morans I

While the heat map indicates the locations of clustering of students' homes and gives a good visual of how closely clustered students' homes are to each other, it does not show statistical significance. To strengthen the statistical analysis, the Cluster and Outlier Analysis (*Anselin Local Morans I*) tool in ArcMap was utilized. This cluster and outlier analysis highlights CBGs that are either statistically more or less clustered than the landscape of the rest of the data set. Like a heat map, this analysis draws attention to those CBGs that are statistically different from the overall spatial pattern of the data set. The

first step was to sum together the number of students' homes by CBG using a spatial join process in ArcMap. Then, these weighted CBG areas or polygons were used to identify the locations of hot spots, cold spots, and areas containing outliers. Existing student family home locations were overlaid with ESRI *LifeMode* Summary Groups at the block group level to quantify and analyze which categories were most representative of the study school students.

RESULTS

A total of 281 student addresses were successfully geo-referenced (address matched); however, 4 were located outside of the Connecticut state boundary and therefore were excluded from this study. This left 277 student addresses for this study. Gender demographics for the study school students in the current study were 74.0% female and 26.0% male. These numbers reflected a gender bias experienced by many HTM programs, which enroll more female than male students. Lee, Olds, and Lee (2010) found the majority of the 1,315 HTM students they surveyed were female (58.5% female respondents). Multiple ring buffers were created in ESRI's ArcMap product to create the following buffers surrounding the campus: 1) under 10 miles; 2) between 10 and 20 miles, 3) between 20 and 30 miles, 4) between 30 and 40 miles, and 5) further than 40 miles. As indicated in Figure 1, the number of student homes in each category summed to 108, 86, 43, 22, and 18 students in each buffer ring, respectively. Thirty-nine percent (39.0%) of student's homes were located within 10 miles of campus. 70.0% were located within 20 miles and 85.6% were located within 30 miles of campus. This indicates that location to campus could be a determining factor for why students apply to the study school. This supports Hypothesis 1, which states that students whose families live closer to campus are more likely to attend the study school.

On the heat map in Figure 2, darker shades of purple indicate where student homes are close to each other or clustered together. The location of campus is not a part of this analysis but instead this map captures each homes proximity to each other – how much they are clustered together. An interesting observation based on the heat map is there appears to be a clustering of current students (as indicated by the darker purple color on the map) around the following locations: the study school campus; an area west of campus in the Bristol, CT area, as well as east of

Figure 1: Ten (10) Mile Buffers from Campus

Figure 2: Heat Map of HTM Students' Family Homes

Hartford near the town of Manchester. This supports H1.

The Cluster and Outlier Analysis (*Anselin Local Morans I*) tool in ArcMap was utilized to show statistically significant groupings of weighted CBGs by number of current students within a given CBG. The tool identified dense clusters of student homes within CBGs and highlighted clustering within the CGB with a beige color. These are the CBGs where there are the greatest clustering of current students and represent a prime target for recruiting activities/ mailings. This also supports H1.

One fact that is important in the following analysis is that the study school is shown to be one of the four most economical options for any student in the state of Connecticut who pursues a four-year degree in Connecticut and is one of the most economical four-year degrees in the HTM major. Hypothesis 2 assesses that many students chose the study school because it was their most economical choice. There were five (5) ESRI *LifeMode* Summary Groups that dominated existing students' homes: High Society, 34.3%; Upscale Avenues, 24.9%; Traditional Living, 11.9%; Senior Styles, 12.6%; Global Roots, 9.0%, and other 7.2%. The large numbers of 'High Society' *LifeMode* students were not anticipated based on the study school's economic price point.

Table 4: HTM Student Count by ESRI Tapestry *LifeMode*

Life Mode	Count	Percentage
High Society	95	34.3%
Upscale Avenues	69	24.9%
Traditional Living	33	11.9%
Senior Styles	35	12.6%
Global Roots	25	9.0%
Other	20	7.2%
Total	277	100.0%

All five of the psychographic groupings were spread out across Connecticut; therefore, location is not evidently associated with the *LifeModes* themselves. The locations of student homes with the psychographic designation of High Society were not clustered in one location. In other words, not all 'High Society' students appeared to be in close to proximity to each other or even close to campus. Instead, their locations across the state indicate the demographics are more important than the location of the CBGs which were tagged with this lifestyle label. This pattern was duplicated with the locations of the other *LifeModes* as well.

All captured CBGs were assigned either a designation of I or II. The I designation was for an

Figure 3: Cluster and Outlier Analysis (*Anselin Local Morans I*)

Table 5: Income Effect on Distance

Income Factor	<10 miles	Between 10 and 20 miles	>20 miles
I	64.81%	68.52%	67.59%
II	35.19%	11.11%	12.04%
	n=108	n=86	n=86

affluent CGB label and a II designation indicated a lack of affluence for the CBG. Thus, according to Table 5, there appears to be no substantial difference among the various distance buffers, which supports Hypothesis 2, which says, “*Students from higher income households are more likely to attend a college of their choice irrespective of the distance from home.*” Further, this same table also supports Hypothesis 1, which states that, “*Students from lower income households are more likely to attend a college that is located closer to their home.*” As can be seen from the table, the income factor II row indicates that lower-income students live within ten miles from the college. Further, please review the following table of hypotheses along with their each level of support for each hypothesis.

CONCLUSIONS

Home addresses from 277 HTM students between 2013 and 2020 were spatially analyzed to determine if there was clustering of students’ homes and to determine if the Retail Gravity Model implied that students typically attend a school located in close proximity to their home of origin. Based on student families’ proximity to the University of concern, this hypothesis was validated (H3) Specifically, distance buffers were applied around the campus into five distance bands based on ten-mile buffer zones. A heat map illustrated those areas with the greatest amount of clustering of homes and the Cluster and Outlier

Analysis (*Anselin Local Morans I*) tool in ArcGIS showed statistically significant groupings of weighted CBGs based on the number of current students within Census Block Group. Additionally, each student’s home address was identified within a CBG – each of which was assigned an ESRI Tapestry *LifeMode* (a psychographic categorization). These categories were tallied to determine the most prominent Tapestry segments among current students. One interesting finding was that almost 60% of all students came from wealthy families based on the two psychographic categories (*High Society* and *Upscale Avenues*).

Although the study school was shown to be one of the most economical choices for a HTM major in the state of Connecticut, almost sixty percent of students’ home locations indicate they came from wealthy families. Further, these wealthy homes were spread out through the state and were not concentrated near the campus. Although this type of GIS analysis requires a substantial amount of expertise with a GIS software, many larger universities have GIS expertise housed in their Geography department; therefore, collaboration could make this type of process feasible for any Tourism and/or Hospitality professor to perform a similar analysis.

Limitations

This study was limited to students attending one university in Connecticut and may not be generalizable to the rest of the United States. Also, this study did not capture an exhaustive list of possible reasons students chose to attend the study school. In fact, this state university may be somewhat unique in its local draw of students. Possible reasons could include choosing a given college where their friends or family attend/attended or that hold some

Table 6: Hypotheses Results

Hypotheses	Results	Analysis
H1 Students are more likely to attend a college that is located closer to their family home.	Supported	Statistics & GIS
H2 Students are more likely to attend a college irrespective of the distance from their family home.	Supported	Statistics & GIS
H3 Students from lower income households are more likely to attend a college that has a lower tuition cost structure.	Not Supported	Statistics & GIS
H4 Students from higher income households are more likely to attend a college of their choice irrespective the college’s tuition cost structure.	Supported	Statistics & GIS
H5 Students’ choice of a college is affected by their demographic and psychographic attributes.	Supported	GIS

positive memory from a campus visit, etc. Additionally, the family home of origin may not be representative of each student's financial standing. For example, some students may be paying for their own college education regardless of their family's socioeconomic profile. Therefore, they may choose the most economical option because their family of origin was not paying their tuition.

These results may have been skewed since only two state schools offer an HTM-type of major in the state of Connecticut – although there are many private offerings for the HTM major, which offer more options for students who are financially more advantaged (or who may earn scholarships). Therefore, results may be different in other states where students have a larger number of cost-effective education options. Additionally, the granting of scholarships by other schools was not considered in this study's analysis. This study focused on GIS-based market segmentation approaches.

Future Studies

A similar analysis could be conducted in states outside of Connecticut to determine how generalizable the results may be related to the rest of the United States. To complete this recruitment exercise, recruitment materials would need to be sent to addresses near those 'hot spots' of current students' homes of origin. Additionally, materials could also be sent to CBGs characterized by the top two psychographic *LifeModes* (identified in this study — High Society and Upscale Avenues) that are located near the campus. This would combine two aspects of this analysis which would maximize the potential of attracting interested, prospective students. A full SWOT analysis would also be helpful to better identify why students choose to attend the study school. The buffers created in Figure 1 are based on Euclidian distances (e.g., as the crow flies) from the campus, but an even more precise method would be to use a street network to determine drive times from student's homes to campus using ESRI's Network Analysis tool.

Future surveys could query students about their decisions to attend based on Lee, Olds, and Lee's (2010) criteria of "'Self-actualization,' 'Job opportunity,' 'Field attractiveness,' 'Foreign experience,' 'External influence,' and 'Ease of Study.'" (p. 24). This could benefit further studies based on work initiated by Lee, et al. Instead of asking an open-ended question about why students chose a major of HTM, these six criteria could be specified to determine if there are more correlations

among these reasons. Further issues could be researched such as if specific learning outcomes are sought by students, as mentioned by Reich, Collins, DeFranco, and Pieper (2019) as well as the desire for human versus nonhuman school brands as described in ul Haq and Bonn (2018). Lastly, the suggestions from Pretlow III (2014) should be further explored and tested in order to explore the merits of personal contact and "multiple exposures" to potential students. These seem to be wise words to heed and further investigate.

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